

AMC Providers / Distributors

Socio-demographics

1. What is your title?
2. What is your training and education level?
3. How long have you worked for the AMC?
4. What positions and titles have you had during your career? At which companies or institutions? What types of companies or institutions are they?

Provision of Services to NICUs and SNCUs

1. What happens when your AMC receives a call from a NICU / SNCU stating that a piece of equipment under your contract needs repair? What is the work flow?
2. What education and training is required for technicians?
3. Do you keep records of maintenance visits? Do you track via job cards? What details are recorded (makes/models, diagnoses, timelines)?
4. What is the payment process? Do you receive performance-based payments, or is the contract a single sum for all work?
5. What services and warranty terms are included in the contract? What is not included?
6. What do you do if a piece of equipment is broken beyond repair?
7. What challenges do you face in working with and communicating with the hospital or facility? What about with other departments in the Ministry of Health?
8. Do you interact with equipment manufacturers? Do work with the manufacturer on warranty fulfillment? Are there any gaps with that process?
9. What are the most common NICU / SNCU equipment failures encountered?
10. What are the most common spare parts used for NICU / SNCU equipment?
11. What equipment are you most often called out for? What fixes are required again and again? Why do you think that is?
12. Do you ever collect/receive feedback from end users (medical care providers and biomedical engineers)? And do you ever report feedback to manufacturers? If yes, what type of information is being exchanged?
13. Are there certain equipment issues that are non-serviceable? What are they and why is service unavailable/not an option?

Recommendations to improve equipment processes:

1. What recommendations do you have for improving the management of lifesaving equipment in the NICU / SNCU?
2. Do you have anything else you would like to add?

Thank you for your participation!

Equipment Manufacturers & Designers

Socio-demographics

1. What is your title?
2. What is your training and education level?

3. How long have you worked at the company?
4. What positions and titles have you had during your career? At which companies or institutions? What types of companies or institutions are they?

NICU and SNCU Equipment

1. Do you work directly with hospitals? Do you work directly with hospitals' or facilities' AMC providers?
2. Do you work with a distributor or do you do your own distribution? If you work with distributors, what is the workflow? Does the distributor handle spare parts as well?
3. What are the typical services and warranty terms?
4. Do you receive feedback from the users? If so, how? What kind of feedback do you receive?
5. How do you ensure the users know about them and budget for them ?
6. What is your design and iteration process? How do you make improvements to the existing equipment? What are the greatest influencing factors for one design over the other? (i.e., cost, complexity, customer's needs)
7. How is procurement done? Who approaches you? What is the process for procurement of the equipment vs. spare parts? (or is it all on the distributor?)
8. Do you produce spare parts for your equipment? Do you provide them under warranty? Is there a system for procuring them after warranty? How long do you continue to make and provide spare parts for a piece of equipment you sell (in years)?
9. Do you provide clear information/installation guides for consumables, accessories, and spare parts?
10. In which countries do you manufacture your products?
11. Are most of your sales domestic or for export? Why?
12. Do you produce equipment according to top-down specifications from entities such as WHO or the government? Do you design equipment to meet the needs of end users? Are you aware of any gaps between top-down specifications and end user needs? Do you attempt to reconcile those?
13. How do you deal with cleaning of equipment? Do you train people on that?
14. How often are problems you're seeing with equipment due to power fluctuations?
15. What are the most common maintenance actions and repairs? What are the most common spare parts used? How do you identify and classify the failure modes?

Challenges and Priorities

1. What are the key challenges and pain points around equipment design and manufacturing?
2. What are your biggest concerns as an equipment designer and manufacturer and what are the current priorities you are trying to address around design, manufacturing, and needs of the end users?

Performance Monitoring

1. How do you define, assess, and measure actual performance of equipment?
 - a. Is regular maintenance or calibration required to keep it performance to spec?
 - b. What are the metrics and indicators around performance, usability, and reliability?
2. Are there processes/mechanisms to help you get information and feedback once equipment is sold to help you know if it is working, what users might want, etc.?
 - a. How do you think about maximizing impact?
 - b. How do the different stakeholders you work with think about maximizing impact?

- c. Is it sales? Is it performance? Is it actual use? Which areas have the biggest gap and can have the most impact if addressed?
3. What types of data would be most actionable for you in the design, manufacturing, and maintenance process?
 - a. Does your equipment generate/log this? Have you done any surveys/landscape of the different classes of SNCU / NICU equipment and what these systems generate and log?

Assumptions and Trends

1. What are the current trends and practices in manufacturing that we should be aware of?
2. Who influences the demand for new design of equipment in this sector?
3. We hear that equipment is often not designed to work in the Indian context, for example handling power outages and fluctuations/irregularities. What are your thoughts on that? Is there anything else besides power that is different from other contexts?
4. What certifications/safety regulations must you consider in the process? What are the biggest challenges for you around these standards? Do standards impose more difficulty to you as an equipment designer/manufacturer?
 - a. Who is the regulatory body for SNCU / NICU equipment?

Stakeholder Engagement

1. What are the biggest concerns of your clients who are purchasing your equipment? (cost/price, maintenance, warranty, service, usability, lifetime, etc.)
2. Do partners/agencies in this sector provide feedback and needs assessments?
3. Do you interface with maintenance technicians/teams/service providers? Is it successful? Where are the problems and what could be done better?
4. How has your design and engagement process changed over time? Where do you want to see the sector go?

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